

Integrating Structural Biology

Instruct-ULTRA

WP8 – Roadmap to the future of Instruct

Lead Beneficiaries: P8 – CSIC, P2- UOXF

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Deliverable D8.2 Process plan for raw and metadata archiving in subtask 8.1.2

Contractual delivery date: 31 December 2019

Actual delivery date: 23 January 2020

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Project objective

To increase the quality and integration of the data being acquired at all installations, including home laboratories, promoting the incorporation of the appropriate metadata and exploring ways to provide archive of raw original data produced at all Instruct -ERIC Centres with appropriate Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs).

Executive summary

We report on work conducted to define a common metadata archive and retrieval process for Instruct-ERIC facilities. Building on approaches developed for protein crystallography, we propose an extension of the ISPyB and ICAT metadata catalogues that can become a more generic solution for other techniques used within life sciences (e.g. Cryo-EM). The report describes an approach and roadmap that can be used to enable facilities across Instruct-ERIC centres to adopt common technology. Once common metadata is stored across facilities this will enable consistent retrieval of data across the consortium and provide rich data for future research.

1. Introduction

Work Package 8 of the Instruct-ULTRA programme focuses on increasing the quality and integration of the data acquired across Instruct-ERIC Centres, promoting the incorporation of appropriate metadata, and exploring ways to provide a permanent archive of the original, raw data.

Task 8.2 focuses on metadata archive and retrieval in accordance with Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles.

The aim of this report (sub task 8.1.2) is to provide an Instruct-wide metadata service, including exploration of raw data archival. The goal is to design a system able to keep metadata produced at all Instruct Centres publicly accessible and query-able, together with a link to the original data.

The work has been carried out by Diamond Light Source, UK (third party to P2 – UOXF) and Centro Nacional de Biotecnología, Centro Superior de Investigaciones Científicas Spain (P8 – CSIC).

2. Current landscape

The Instruct-ULTRA project was established to promote and enhance structural biology research services across the life sciences. It also provides a community to share best practice and foster collaboration between research centres. Its membership includes large national facilities (including synchrotrons, such as Diamond) as well as academic and industrial centres.

There is a growing desire for research organisations to promote open science and publish data in accordance with FAIR principles [\[1\]](#). While Instruct-ULTRA is focused on structural biology there are a number of related programmes seeking to enable the use of FAIR data across scientific disciplines. Two such programmes are Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud (PanOSC) [\[2\]](#) and European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Services (ExPaNDS) [\[3\]](#), funded as Horizon 2020 projects. These collaborations aim to develop standard data and analysis services for photon and neutron light sources across Europe. They are both part of the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative. Within Instruct, the EOSC Life project [\[4\]](#) is seeking to provide a digital collaboration space for biological sciences within the context of EOSC.

However, exactly what metadata should be published to provide value to researchers is still to be defined.

Many light sources across Europe use the Information System for Protein Crystallography (ISPyB) Laboratory Information Management System [5] to store metadata. ISPyB was developed as common approach for large scale facilities to store metadata for protein crystallography. ISPyB has evolved to include multiple techniques including BioSAXS and CryoEM. The metadata stored in ISPyB is very rich, covering the lifecycle of an experiment. It includes metadata for shipping, sample information, crystal screens, processing results, links to published structures such as the Protein Data Bank (PDB) as well as facility wide reporting and statistics. A subset of the rich metadata is typically copied to a data catalogue such as ICAT (Information CATalogue) [6] along with raw and processed data. This process was described in the previous report in this work package [7]. The combination of ISPyB and ICAT allow researchers to find their historical data for post experiment review and analysis. However, researchers are not able to search for data conducted by a third-party institution.

3. Future Landscape

In the next few years, more scientific facilities will be adopting an open data policy for publicly funded research. As such, an increasing amount of information will need to be made available to researchers across the life sciences. Instruct-ERIC is well placed to provide common services to the life science community, by leveraging and sharing best practice across its members.

Large scale facilities will continue to develop data catalogues and Information Management Systems with increasing integration between them. These systems can be exploited across INSTRUMENT centres. However, it is worth noting that data catalogues such as ICAT and SciCAT [8] are designed to be generic and hence are not optimised for structural biology. It is also the case that they tend to store a subset of published/final data rather than everything conducted during a session. They are complimentary to an experiment information management system (such as ISPyB) that includes rich metadata. In future, we can assume that data catalogues will continue to provide an initial view of experiments conducted at a facility. An illustration of the relationship between generic data catalogue metadata and rich experimental metadata is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Relationship between publications, data catalogue and experimental data

Conceivably, a common Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) that could be deployed easily across Instruct centres with suitable search and retrieval services could be provided through programmes developed by Instruct-ERIC. These programmes would allow smaller institutions to take advantage of rich metadata with suitable integration services. As we described in the previous report [7], Instruct could provide an ICAT service to smaller Research Institutes (RIs).

The ability to search and identify experiments of interest will only be practical if sufficiently rich metadata is stored alongside the raw and processed data. Therefore, the rich metadata available in systems such as ISPyB could be exploited to enhance existing data catalogues. Figure 2 illustrates this by showing how a user may be able to “drill down” from a publication identified via a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), access a data catalogue to identify datasets, and then in future harvest more metadata (e.g. processing software versions used) from an Experiment Information Management System.

Figure 2 User accessing hierarchy of metadata from DOI to experiment information

Future EOSC services may be able to recover and restage data along with instances of the processing software used to analyse the data. This vision will only work if sufficiently rich metadata is stored for each experiment.

4. Description of work

Work conducted under this task is based on lessons from deployment of an Electronic Information Management System (EIMS) and Data Catalogue at Diamond Light Service (DLS). It also describes what changes need to be implemented to provide a common solution across Instruct centres. A roadmap is presented at the end of this section to summarise steps required to implement the vision.

Based on the anticipated future landscape, the requirements for a common Instruct metadata capability can be described as follows:

- A data catalogue provided as a service
- EIMS that is easy to deploy and setup for facilities with limited support
- EIMS integration with local processing pipelines
- EIMS provided support services (e.g. session administration) and/or integration with third party services
- FAIR data services Application Processing Interface (API) i.e. export/expose metadata for published and open data sets

While a data catalogue could be hosted by an Instruct-ERIC cloud service (see reference [7]), experimental information management systems need to be closely coupled to acquisition and analysis of raw data. The working assumption, therefore, is that a local LIMS will be required on site which can provide metadata services either directly or to a third party data catalogue.

On that basis some key features of ISPyB need to be developed in order that it can provide a common solution for a wider variety of institutes. We have coined the term “MyISPyB” to represent this new approach.

Figure 3 - MyISPyB concept building on SynchWeb and ISPyB database

The main development needs which are discussed in the following sections can be summarised as:

- Deployment tools and environment configuration
- Supporting services for user/proposal administration
- Database refactoring
 - Methods to extend database schema with new sample types (not everything is a protein)
- Develop services to support standard metadata harvesting protocols

4.1 Deployment tools

The ISPyB software stack consists of a relational database, web services and a user interface. There are two main implementations of ISPyB at this point. An original Java based framework subject to a collaboration agreement and a more recent PHP implementation. This report will focus on the latter; a Linux, Apache, MySQL and PHP (LAMP) stack in operation at Diamond (i.e. SynchWeb [\[9\]](#)). While the software implementations differ, the underlying database schema is consistent and evolves through the collaboration.

Lessons from the collaboration indicate that facilities can struggle to get setup with ISPyB due to limited resources and the complexity of the technology. Therefore, to reduce the “barrier to entry” we have created a virtual environment that creates a full software stack using Virtual Machines (VMs). The process uses Vagrant to build VMs and Ansible (a provisioning system) to build the software. The benefit of a tool such as Ansible is that it provides a simple description of the instructions required to build applications (using YAML files). Vagrant is able to read the files (called playbooks) to build and provision the VM. The Ansible playbooks can also be used to install the same software on physical machines or containers if required. Single or Multiple VMs can be configured in this way to provide supporting services (e.g. Central Authentication Service (CAS)).

Figure 4 - Ansible playbook contains instructions to build the ISPyB database and web applications

As a test we installed a version at the CSIC in order to test integration with Scipion [\[10\]](#) and EM data collections. The installation scripts are available as open source on GitHub [\[11\]](#). Other synchrotrons across Europe and North America have also used this process to get up and running with ISPyB.

Additional APIs are also available in python and Java to help integrate acquisition systems with ISPyB. In future, the deployment approach can be enhanced to deploy MyISPyB as a set of containers providing micro services along with sample data sets if required.

4.2 Supporting services for user/proposal administrations

The metadata in ISPyB provides a solid foundation for common metadata across Instruct centres. However, ISPyB focuses on experiment metadata and is deployed at large scale facilities as part of a systems approach; integrated with other tools such as:

- Proposal management
- Beamline scheduling
- Processing tools and pipelines

So ISPyB on its own does not provide an “out of the box” capability without additional services (or low level database administration). Critically, proposal and user management are missing from the software implementations. To mitigate that issue we have developed some basic functionality in Synchweb to add/edit proposals and sessions.

A screenshot of the SynchWeb web application interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Calendar', 'Logout', 'diamond' logo, 'Reporting', 'Logistics', and 'Stats'. Below the navigation is a breadcrumb trail: 'Proposals & Visits > Add Proposal'. A secondary navigation bar contains 'Proposals', 'cy1234 v', 'Projects', 'Unit Cell Search', 'Feedback', and 'Help'. A green message bar states 'This is the message of the day.' The main content area is titled 'Add New Proposal' and contains a form with the following fields: 'Code' (Proposal code usually indicating type of proposal) with value 'em'; 'Number' (Unique proposal number) with value '3001'; 'Title' (The proposal title) with value 'Cryo-EM Investigation of ...'; and 'Primary Investigator' (The proposal PI) with value '46270'. An 'Add Proposal' button is located below the form. At the bottom of the page, there is a link: 'SynchWeb? What is This?'.

Figure 5 - Adding a proposal to ISPyB through SynchWeb UI

A user with administrator privileges (i.e. specifically the “manage_proposals” permission) has the ability to add proposals in ISPyB. Once a proposal is added a user with those administrator privileges can create sessions within the specific proposal (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Adding a session to a proposal via SynchWeb

The forms are somewhat basic and could be better served by a common cloud solution such as that provided by ARIA [12]. However, they allow a site to start with MyISPyB including basic administration functions through the web based user interface.

What is not covered by ARIA are domain specific processing pipelines. During this work package we have also demonstrated integration between ISPyB and Scipion. The high level architecture is shown in Figure 7 below. Integration with ISPyB is handled via an ActiveMQ based architecture (called Zocalo) to provide a loose coupling between the processing tools and SynchWeb services. A similar conceptual approach could be adopted by other tools so long as the ISPyB database schema supports their needs.

Figure 7 - Integration between SynchWeb/ISPyB and Scipion processing tool

4.3 Database refactoring to support wider structural biology

As the acronym indicates ISPyB has its roots in protein crystallography. While the focus has traditionally been on the field of macro-molecular crystallography we are seeing growing interest in extending ISPyB to support other disciplines. Electron microscopy in particular has been the focus for collaborative work through the ISPyB collaboration and under this work package. ISPyB now includes some EM specific tables to capture sample images/movies and motion correction metadata. Integration with EM processing tools (e.g. Scipion) has also been demonstrated. However, the current database schema could be improved and simplified to make it easier to add new experimental techniques and samples.

ISPyB consists of over 200 tables with complex relationships; therefore refactoring the database schema will be a long task. Some small steps could be taken to improve the situation though. Initially changing the sample descriptions such that not everything is assumed to be a protein would be a step forwards. The current subset of tables that

describe a sample in ISPyB are shown in Figure 8. Note that not all tables will be discussed in this report due to the size and scope of the work.

Figure 8 - Current ISPyB tables that describe samples

As shown in Figure 8, the BeamLineSample (BLSample) table represents an instance of a sample placed within the beam. The Protein table represents the type of material being analysed and it may take multiple crystalline forms; hence a separate Crystal table. The ComponentType table is a way to indicate that the sample could be a Protein, RNA, DNA etc.

The DiffractionPlan table again shows the origin of the schema and the initial design assumption that all experiments would be x-ray diffraction measurements. This is despite the fact that actual measurements are recorded in a DataCollection table.

A revised version which is more generic is illustrated in Figure 9. In this example a more generic term DataCollectionPlan is used in place of DiffractionPlan. Also the Protein/Crystal tables are renamed SampleMaterial and SampleProperties. The practical

considerations of making this change are in active discussion through the ISPyB collaboration. It may be the case that the current tables are left and new SampleMaterial/SampleProperties tables are added in parallel. That way existing sites using ISPyB can continue to use the current tables while the generalisation activity takes place.

Figure 9 - Proposed Sample tables to make ISPyB more suited to new techniques

The use of ISPyB across Instruct is not without its challenges. The database schema is effective at describing crystallography experiments for a certain class of samples. However, efforts to expand its scope to include EM techniques have been successful and there is interest in continuing to evolve the schema to support new samples and data collection methods. It is also open source and therefore open for scientists and developers to build on the work conducted to date.

4.4 Metadata harvesting protocols

There are other large EU projects investigating the definition of metadata standards for Photon and Neutron sources. Some research and experimentation within those

communities has investigated the use of the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) standard [13]. This standard provides a generic approach to allow third party systems to harvest metadata.

It is likely that data catalogues such as ICAT and SciCat will have such an API in future. However, as previously mentioned these catalogues are limited in what levels and scales of metadata that can be stored. The experience from DLS is that in practice only a small amount of metadata can be stored per dataset due to the vast numbers of datasets generated on site. Smaller institutions may not have this limitation. In any case, the use of a LIMS/EIMS provides more flexibility in future, however, and can provide a more comprehensive set of metadata for datasets. Users could in future “drill down” to a rich set of metadata captures about the experiment including processing results, software versions used, detector setup and configuration.

Figure 10 - Addition of a public API to MyISPyB would provide a coherent metadata harvesting service across Instruct Research Infrastructures (RIs).

A new service as part of MyISPyB could, therefore, become a provider of metadata using the OAI-PMH protocol. The implementation would need to be constructed such that only public/open access datasets and investigations would be available. Links to these services (i.e. MyISPyB URLs) could be stored in the Instruct data catalogue(s). In the case of ICAT (using its current schema [14]) a dataset or investigation can be extended by defining a new ParameterType (e.g. OAI-PMH_Provider) which provides a URL to harvest the rich metadata in ISPyB. The data catalogue front end would need to be extended to provide user access to this source of information, but the technology and protocols could at least be standardised.

4.3 Summary

The proposals described in this task need to be developed further if they are to be adopted broadly across Instruct centres. Initially the proposals can be exploited through the ISPyB collaboration as indicated in Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Roadmap for continuation of MyISPyB through collaboration and exploitation of EU research programmes

As shown in figure 11, the ongoing work from the PanOSC and EXPANDS projects will also refine the ideas described in this report.

6. Conclusions and Recommendations

- Data catalogues and Experiment Information Management systems are mature technologies for life sciences research conducted at large scale facilities;
- There is a growing interest in extending data catalogues from Photon and Neutron facilities to help define future services as part of EOSC;
- Unlocking consistent rich metadata could be possible through the adoption of MyISPyB; a set of services built around the ISPyB database and ecosystem;
- Adoption of a common protocol (such as OAI-PMH) would allow Instruct RIs to support future open access research consistent with FAIR principles; and
- Additional development work is required to make ISPyB suitable for a larger range of sites, but as the technology is open source, additional contributions can be made by the wider community.

7. References

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